

Synthesis of orthorhombic MoO₃ nanosheets for visible-light-driven photocatalytic application

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Abstract

Recently, significant attention has been paid to degradation of organic dyes/effluents since the huge utilization of organic dyes/chemicals in the industries which affect the water ecosystem and cause environmental pollution. Thus, the synthesis of earth abundant and non-precious metal oxide/sulfide photocatalysts are highly warranted for large scale photocatalytic applications. Until now, the different semiconductor materials such as TiO₂, ZnO, Fe₂O₃, ZnS, MoO₃ and WO₃ have been synthesized and reported as the effective photo catalysts for the degradation of organic dyes (1, 2). Among them, MoO₃ has attracted much more attention in various fields due to its layered structure and easily variable oxidation states (3, 4). In this work, sheet like α -MoO₃ nanostructures were synthesized by simple hydrothermal method for photocatalytic applications. XRD results reveal that the synthesized MoO₃ nanostructure is a pure orthorhombic phase (α -MoO₃) with highly crystalline in nature. The characteristic vibration of Mo and O atoms in MoO₃ nanostructure were evidently confirmed by FTIR analysis. The optical band gap energy 3.07 eV was calculated from UV-Vis DRS spectroscopy. FE-SEM images indicated that the synthesized α -MoO₃ have sheet like morphology. Furthermore, the synthesized α -MoO₃ were used as photocatalyst for the degradation of methylene blue and rhodamine B organic dyes.

Keywords: Hydrothermal method, MoO₃ nanostructures, Photocatalyst, Organic dyes

References

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